

Fig. 1.

DSS2 Red

DSS2 Blue

PanSTARRS

AllWISE

AKARI FIS

IRAS-IRIS

Deep Optical Imaging

Figure 1. Multi-wavelength view of the cloud associated with IRAS 19448–0234. Top row (left to right): DSS2 Red (inverted greyscale), DSS2 Blue (inverted greyscale), PanSTARRS DR1 colour composite (g, z bands). Middle row: AllWISE colour composite (W1 3.4 μm , W2 4.6 μm , W4 22 μm), AKARI FIS colour composite (N60 65 μm , WIDE-S 90 μm , WIDE-L 140 μm), IRAS-IRIS (100 μm). Bottom: deep optical image obtained by the author (>24h integration), with a 10' scale bar. All panels are similarly oriented and centred on RA 19h 47m 30s, Dec $-02^{\circ} 27' 07''$ (J2000). The morphological consistency of the cloud structure across optical extinction and far-infrared thermal emission is evident across all panels.